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**SARS-COV-2 INFECTION AND VIRULENCE: ARE THE
ANTI-SARS-COV-2 VACCINES DEVELOPED BY
PFIZER/BIONTECH, MODERNA AND JOHNSON &
JOHNSON EFFECTIVE AND SAFE?**

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Abstract.

SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19 have wreaked havoc in the lives and economies of most countries around the world. Only a few countries have been able to control SARS-COV-2 infections and deaths due to COVID-19. As opposed to the proven response strategy consisting of , many countries, including the United States have decided to solely rely on the so-called "Herd Immunity" by vaccinating their population various anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccines that were developed by private Pharmaceutical and Biotechnological Companies, including Pfizer/BioNTech, Moderna and Johnson and Johnson. It has been argued that large-scale vaccination is the only way to preventing SARS-COV-2 infection and COVID-19 deaths, and that there will be light at the end of the tunnel as a result of mass-vaccination with the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccines that were developed by private Pharmaceutical and Biotechnological Companies, including Pfizer/BioNTech, Moderna and Johnson and Johnson. A student of the Art of War will question the wisdom of putting all of the eggs in one basket. The following questions must be asked and answered: 1. Is it reasonable to expect that the technology used to develop anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccines will perform as expected? 2. Is it a reasonable strategy to expect that the development

and testing of anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccines can be performed in less than a year? 3. Are the developed vaccines really effective? 4. Is it reasonable to expect that the population at large can be vaccinated with a safe and effective vaccine. There can be no "Herd Immunity" in the absence of an effective and safe vaccine. Unfortunately, the figures speak for themselves and they tend to show that the strategy of using currently available anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccines to achieve so-called "Herd Immunity" is not rational and ill-advised.

SARS-COV-2, the etiologic agent of COVID-19 [1-4] have wreaked havoc in the lives and economies in most countries around the world. Only a few countries have been able to control SARS-COV-2 infections and deaths due to COVID-19. As opposed to the proven response strategy consisting of Isolation/Confinement, Mask Wearing, Social Distancing, Testing, Contact Tracing and Treatment (IMSTCT), many countries, including the United States, United Kingdom, Canada, France and Germany have decided to rely solely on the so-called "Herd Immunity" by vaccinating their population with various anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccines that were developed by private Pharmaceutical and Biotechnological Companies, including Pfizer/BioNTech, Moderna and Johnson and Johnson. There can be no "Herd Immunity" without an effective and safe vaccine. In the United States, the government and the experts and pundits have argued that large-scale

vaccination is the only way to preventing SARS-COV-2 infection and COVID-19 deaths, and that there will be light at the end of the tunnel as a result of mass-vaccination with the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccines that were developed by private Pharmaceutical and Biotechnological Companies, including Pfizer/BioNTech, Moderna and Johnson and Johnson. Are the assumptions that only mass vaccination will lead to semblance of normal life. Past experience with HIV-1, SARS-COV-1 and H1N1 argues against achieving "Herd Immunity" with vaccines. A student of the Art of War will question the wisdom of putting all of the eggs in one basket. The following questions must be asked and answered: 1. Is it reasonable to expect that the technology used to develop anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccines will perform as expected? 2. Is it a reasonable strategy to expect that the development and testing of anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccines can be performed in less than a year? 3. Are the developed vaccines really

effective? 4. Is it reasonable to expect that the population at large can be vaccinated with a safe and effective vaccine.

The Pfizer/BioNTech anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine (BNT162b2mRNA) [5,6]:

According to the United States Center for Disease Control, "mRNA vaccine is made of mRNA wrapped in a coating that makes delivery easy and keeps the body from damaging it and that the mRNA in the vaccine teaches the cell how to make copies of the spike protein and that if you are exposed to the real virus later, your body will recognize it and know how to fight it". It must be noted that a mRNA vaccine has never been shown to be successful at preventing any diseases or infections prior to its use to control COVID-19. It must also be noted that the mRNA vaccine developed by Pfizer/BioNTech (BNT162b2mRNA) does not prevent SARS-COV-2 infection is well accepted and acknowledged by Pfizer/BioNTech. However, it is claimed that the BNT162b2mRNA vaccine does prevent severe symptoms of COVID-19 and death due to COVID-19, and that it is safe to be injected into humans [5,6]. Whether the latter claim is borne out by the data obtained from the clinical trial [6] is the subject of this scientific investigative critique.

The first red flag with respect to the testing of the effectiveness and safety of the Pfizer/BioNTech (BNT162b2mRNA) is that the whole process took less than 9 months before it was approved for emergency use by the United States Federal Drug Administration [5,7]. Prior to the Emergency Use Approval (EUA) [7] and full approval of mRNA1273 SARS-COV-2 vaccine (Pfizer/BioNTech is apparently seeking full approval), no vaccine had been developed and approved in such short time [8] (Has there been political pressure to come up with an anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine despite the fact that the technology used and the time devoted to test the technology were unproven and inadequate). As a comparison, there is currently no safe and effective vaccines that have been developed to control HIV-1. It is understandable that Pfizer/BioNTech do not wish to divulge what their anti-SARS-COV-2 mRNA vaccine consists of. According to the FDA [7], the anti-SARS-COV-2 mRNA vaccine (BNT162b2mRNA) consists of the following: "Each 0.3 mL dose of the Pfizer-BioNTech COVID-19 Vaccine contains 30 mcg of a nucleoside modified messenger RNA (modRNA) encoding the viral spike (S) glycoprotein of SARS-CoV-2. The Pfizer-BioNTech COVID-19 Vaccine is supplied as a frozen suspension in multiple dose vials;

each vial must be diluted with 1.8 mL of sterile 0.9% Sodium Chloride Injection, USP prior to use to form the vaccine. The Pfizer-BioNTech COVID-19 Vaccine does not contain a preservative. Each dose of the Pfizer-BioNTech COVID-19 Vaccine also includes the following ingredients: lipids (0.43 mg (4-hydroxybutyl)azanediy)bis(hexane-6,1-diyl)bis(2-hexyldecanoate), 0.05 mg 2[(polyethylene glycol)-2000]-N,N-ditetradecylacetamide, 0.09 mg 1,2-distearoyl-sn-glycero-3phosphocholine, and 0.2 mg cholesterol), 0.01 mg potassium chloride, 0.01 mg monobasic potassium phosphate, 0.36 mg sodium chloride, 0.07 mg dibasic sodium phosphate dihydrate, and 6 mg sucrose. The diluent (0.9% Sodium Chloride Injection) contributes an additional 2.16 mg sodium chloride per dose. The dosing regimen is two doses of 0.3 mL".

What is exactly "30 mcg of a nucleoside - modified messenger RNA (modRNA) encoding the viral spike (S) glycoprotein of SARS-CoV-2" It is indeed mind-boggling that a vaccine that is be injected into billions of individuals is described as "30 mcg of a nucleoside modified messenger RNA (modRNA) encoding the viral spike (S) glycoprotein of SARS-CoV-2" [7]. In order

to have an idea of what BNT162b2mRNA vaccine is, one must refer back to the work of the Scientific Researcher, Katalin Kariko [8], initially of Scientific Researcher from Hungary and later a Research Assistant Professor at the University of Pennsylvania (Apparently, Katalin Kariko was demoted because her research output was not considered worthy of being promoted). The work of Kariko, K. et al. [9,10] extends and consolidates the works of Malone et al., Dimitriadis, G.J. and Wolff et al. [11-13]. Essentially, Kariko, K. et al. [9,10] showed that a mRNA complexed to lipofectin could be transfected in cells in culture and incorporation of modified nucleosides in the mRNA molecule prevented the stimulation of the mammalian innate immune system through Toll-like receptors so that deleterious effects of injecting mRNA into cells and tissues could be obviated and production of protein encoded by mRNA could take place with little consequence to the injected host. Although, Pfizer/BioNTech and Katalin Kariko did not set out to use mRNA as a vehicle to produce a vaccine, the technology developed was found to be attractive and applicable with respect to the development of an anti-SARS-COV-2 mRNA vaccine. Essentially the anti-SARS-COV-2 mRNA vaccine (BNT162b2mRNA) developed by

Pfizer/BioNTech consists of mRNA that encodes for SARS-COV-2 S protein with modified nucleosides. While in theory, the the technology developed by Pfizer/BioNTech and Katalin Kariko is simple and elegant, its use to develop an anti-SARS-COV-2 mRNA vaccine is problematic at several levels, including (i) the efficiency of antigen presentation is questionable, (ii) the produced antigen may not be sufficient to elicit an effective immune response, (iii) the efficacy of induced immune response (if any) may be short-lived, (iv) mutations of the SARS-COV-2 encoded S protein are problematic, (v) whether the clinical trial of the anti-SARS-COV-2 can be and has been properly conducted, and (vi) whether there has been Dishonest Scientific Reporting, Data Falsification and Data Fabrication.

(i) The efficiency of antigen presentation and production is questionable and (ii) The produced antigen may not be sufficient to elicit an effective immune response: It has been demonstrated that proteins can be produced from mRNA molecules injected into cells and tissues [10-13]. However, there are no studies that determine the absolute amount of protein that are produced following transfection of cells or injection of tissues. There are also no studies with respect

to the cellular localization of the produced proteins (Presumably, if the proteins are to be presented at the cell surface, the mRNA must contain correct additional sequence. It is not clear whether the anti-SARS-COV-2 mRNA vaccine developed by Pfizer/BioNTech (BNT162b2mRNA) contains sequence unrelated to the SARS-COV-2 encoded S protein). Is the amount of SARS-COV-2 encoded S protein (perhaps containing additional sequence?) that is produced sufficient to elicit the appropriate immune response that would prevent severe symptoms of COVID-19 and death. It is clear that it is not enough to prevent SARS-COV-2 infection which is quite paradoxical. The infection of individuals vaccinated with BNT162b2mRNA is a common occurrence [14] Why does the anti-SARS-COV-2 mRNA vaccine developed by Pfizer/BioNTech (BNT162b2mRNA) prevents severe symptoms of COVID-19 and death but not SARS-COV-2 infection. BNT162b2mRNA is directed at the SARS-COV-2 encoded Spike protein and should in principle prevent SARS-COV-2 infection since SARS-COV-2 encoded Spike protein is essential for binding to the SARS-COV-2 receptor, ACE2 of cells to be infected.

The strategy of using only the SARS-COV-2 encoded Spike protein as immunogen to elicit an immune response against SARS-COV-2 may have been ill-thought and ill-advised for a number of obvious reasons, including mutations of SARS-COV-2 encoded Spike protein (see below) reduced effectiveness of the immune response. Various studies have demonstrated that following SARS-COV-2 infection, the immune system of the host mount a defensive response consisting of producing antibodies that target not just the S protein but also other SARS-COV-2 encoded proteins, in particular the Nucleocapsid protein [15,16]. Interestingly, it was shown that production of antibodies against the Spike and N proteins can be correlated with the severity of disease [15].

(ii) The efficacy of induced immune response (if any) may be short-lived: Mass vaccination of individuals in the United States is currently taking place. According to the CDC, as of May 17, 2021, more than 123 million individuals in the United States have been vaccinated. Already, various experts and pundits, including the CEO of Pfizer are speculating about "booster shots" [17-19]. It is not surprising that "booster shots" would be required since the Pfizer/BioNTech anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine (BNT162b2mRNA)

is essentially an immunogen consisting of a single protein. It has been theorized that long term antibodies production from memory B cells and antibody secreting cells are dependent upon the initial affinity of the antigen/immunogen for newly activated B cells. Apparently, B cells with relatively high affinity for the antigen/immunogen will differentiate into short-lived extrafollicular Antibody Secreting Cells and that B cells of lower affinity develop into GC-independent memory B cells which determine long term immunity [20-24]. It is recommended that studies on the long-term production of antibodies by B memory cells by true experts should be initiated immediately. Furthermore, no studies have been performed to determine whether the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine developed by Pfizer/BioNTech (BNT162b2mRNA) can induce memory B cells in the absence of SARS-COV-2 infection.

According to the CDC, as of April 30, 2021 [25], it has received 10262 reports of vaccine breakthrough infections in 46 U.S. states and territories after 101 million individuals had been fully vaccinated. This represents an IPV-10000 (or Total Number of Individuals Infected with SARS-COV-2 Per 10000 Vaccinated Individuals) of ~1 (Figure 1A).

The IPUV-10000 Number for the clinical trial of the Pfizer/BioNTech anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine (BNT162b2mRNA) was stated (could be calculated) to be ~4 [6] (Figure 1A) while the average IPUV-10000 Number in the general population during the clinical trial of the Pfizer/BioNTech anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine (BNT162b2mRNA) was ~179 [26] (Figure 1).

The discrepancy in the IPUV-10000 Numbers reported in the clinical trial of the Pfizer/BioNTech anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine (BNT162b2mRNA) and the IPUV-10000 Number in the general population during the clinical trial of the Pfizer/BioNTech anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine (BNT162b2mRNA) must somehow be reconciled. If not, suspicion of Data Falsification and Dishonest Scientific Reporting would be legitimate. According to the CDC [25], 160 deaths among vaccinated individuals were recorded which represents a DPV-10000 (Total deaths of Per 10000 Vaccinated Individuals) of ~0.02, compared to DPV-10000 of 0 and DPUV-10000 of 0 during the clinical trials of BNT162b2mRNA [6] (Figure 1B) (These figures show that not enough subjects were enrolled). These results also suggest that the effectiveness of vaccination is questionable. The study of Dagan et al. [27] reveals that in

Israel, the DPV-10000 for individuals vaccinated with BNT162b2mRNA was ~0.15 compared to DPUV-10000 of ~0.54 for unvaccinated individuals.

Figure 1. Panel A, Comparison of IPUV-10000 Number (Total Number of Individuals Infected with SARS-COV-2 and developing COVID-19 Per 10000 Unvaccinated Population) for the general population (I), IPUV-10000 Number (Total Number of Individuals Infected with SARS-COV-2 and developing COVID-19 Per 10000 Unvaccinated Population) for the Pfizer/BioNTech clinical trial (II), and IPV-10000 (Total Number of Individuals Infected with SARS-COV-2 and developing COVID-19 Per 10000 Vaccinated Population). Panel B, Comparison of DPUV-10000 Number (Total Number of Deaths due to SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19 Per 10000 Unvaccinated Population) for the general population (I), DPUV-10000 Number (Total Number of Deaths due to SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19 Per 10000 Unvaccinated Population) for the Pfizer/BioNTech clinical trial (II), and DPV-10000 (Total Number of Deaths due to SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19 Per 10000 Vaccinated Population).

In Israel, the average DPUV-10000 (Total Deaths due to SARS-COV-2/COVID-19 Per 10000 Unvaccinated Population) for the general population is ~6.9 (The discrepancy between DPUV Number of ~0.54 in the study of Dagan et al. [26] and the average DPUV-10000 Number of ~6.9 in the general population in Israel needs to be reconciled!). These figures strongly suggest that the incidence of death due to SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19 was extremely low without vaccination and that vaccination with BNT162b2mRNA was unnecessary. With respect to severe symptoms of COVID-19, the effect of vaccination with BNT162b2mRNA was also quite marginal. The IPV-10000 was ~0.92 compared to IPUV-10000 of ~2.9, again suggesting that the incidence of severe symptoms of COVID-19 was extremely low in Israel. In contrast, in the United States, the average DPUV-10000 Number (Total Deaths due to SARS-COV-2/COVID-19 Per 10000 Population) and the current DPP-10000 (as of May 10, 2021) was ~18 (Figure 1B). As stated above, no death was recorded for either the vaccinated or unvaccinated participants the clinical trial of the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine developed by Pfizer/BioNTech (BNT162b2mRNA). The discrepancy between the DPV-10000 Number of 0 for

vaccinated individual and DPV-10000 Number of 0 for unvaccinated individual observed during the clinical trial of the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine developed by Pfizer/BioNTech (BNT162b2mRNA), and DPUV-10000 Number of ~18 for the general population needs to be reconciled. If not, it is legitimate to invoke the occurrence of Dishonest Scientific Reporting, Data Falsification and possibly Data Fabrication [28,29]. It has been argued that the drop in the number of deaths due to SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19 in Israel and the United States is due to the effectiveness of the of BNT162b2mRNA [6,25]. An alternative explanation is that the decrease in the number of deaths due to SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19 in Israel and the United States is related to the increase temperature, humidity and far infrared irradiation during March 2021 and April 2021. It is no secret that the infectivity and virulence of SARS-COV-2 is inversely correlated with elevated temperature, humidity and far infrared irradiation [30-32].

The true effectiveness and safety of the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine developed by Pfizer/BioNTech can only be determined when a high proportion of individuals in the United States has been fully vaccinated and

most importantly only after fall and winter of 2021-2022.

(iv) Mutations of the SARS-COV-2 encoded S protein are problematic: Many SARS-COV-2 variants with several mutations in the SARS-COV-2 encoded S protein, including B.1.1.7 from the United Kingdom, B.1.351 from South Africa, P.1/P.2 from Brazil, B.1.526 from New York, U.S.A and B.1.6.17 from India have emerged [33-38]. A study by Hacısuleyman, F. et al. [39] describes two cases of breakthrough infections with SARS-COV-2 variants out a total of 417 persons who were vaccinated with the Pfizer/BioNTech vaccine (BNT162b2mRNA) or the Moderna Vaccine (mRNA1273 SARS-CoV-2). A study of Kustin et al. [40] in Israel reported that there was a disproportionate number of breakthrough infections with SARS-COV-2 variants B.1.1.7 and B.1.351. Unfortunately, it is not possible to calculate the IPV-10000 and IPUV-10000 Numbers from the data provided by Kustin et al. [40]. It is important to determine the IVP-10000 and IPUV-10000 Numbers in order to be able to determine the true effectiveness of the Pfizer/BioNTech vaccine (BNT162b2mRNA) in current and future SARS-COV-2/COVID-19 pandemic condition.

(v) Whether the clinical trial of the anti-SARS-COV-2 can be and has been properly conducted and (vi) Whether there has been Dishonest Scientific Reporting, Data Falsification and Data Fabrication: It was previously demonstrated [26] that there are disturbing inconsistencies with the clinical trial of the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine developed by Pfizer/BioNTech (BNT162b2mRNA) [6]. In particular, it was demonstrated that there are major discrepancies between the reported figures of IPUV-10000 and DPUV-10000 for the clinical trial of BNT162b2mRNA and the figures of IPUV-10000 and DPUV-10000 for the general population under prevailing pandemic condition [38] (Figure 1). As described above, it is now quite legitimate to question the claimed effectiveness of the Pfizer/BioNTech vaccine (BNT162b2mRNA) [6]

The clinical trial to determine the efficacy and safety of the Pfizer/BioNTech vaccine (BNT162b2mRNA) [6] involved 36523 participants with no previous history of SARS-COV-2 infections. As discussed above, there were not enough participants to determine the DPV-10000 and DPUV-10000 numbers. It is therefore impossible to determine whether whether Pfizer/BioNTech

vaccine (BNT162b2mRNA) [6] was effective or not (i.e whether it prevents death due to SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19). Polack, F.P. et al. [6] states that the Pfizer/BioNTech vaccine (BNT162b2mRNA) [6] was 95% effective because 8 out of vaccinated participants and 162 out of unvaccinated participants developed COVID-19. The IPV-10000 Number and IPUV-10000 Number for the clinical trial of the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine developed by Pfizer/BioNTech (BNT162b2mRNA) [6] could be calculated to be ~1 and ~4 respectively (Figure 1A). The IPUV-10000 Number for the clinical trial of Pfizer/BioNTech vaccine (BNT162b2mRNA) [6] differed quite markedly from the IPUV-10000 Numbers for the other clinical trials discussed below and the average IPUV-10000 Number of ~179 [26] in the general population during the clinical trial of the Pfizer/BioNTech anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine (BNT162b2mRNA) (Figure 1A). The discrepancy in the IPUV-10000 Numbers reported in the clinical trial of the Pfizer/BioNTech anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine (BNT162b2mRNA) [6] and the IPUV-10000 Number in the general population [179] during the clinical trial of the Pfizer/BioNTech anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine (BNT162b2mRNA) strongly suggest

that Dishonest Scientific Report, Data Falsification and possibly Data Fabrication have taken place (Figure 1A).

Furthermore, the DPUV-10000 Number for the general population during the clinical trial of the Pfizer/BioNTech anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine (BNT162b2mRNA) was ~18 [26] (Figure 1B). These results strongly suggest that the clinical trial of the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine developed by Pfizer/BioNTech (BNT162b2mRNA) with IPV-10000 and IPUV-10000 of 0 [6] was badly designed because it did not reflect the prevailing pandemic condition and the participants were also not reflective of the general population. Designing an experimental protocol in order to obtain a preconceived result and conclusion constitutes Data Falsification [28,29]. Not highlighting and discussing that an experimental protocol that has been designed to produce preconceived results and conclusions constitutes Dishonest Scientific Report [28,29].

A major problem with the clinical trial of the Pfizer/BioNTech vaccine (BNT162b2mRNA) [6] is that it is in fact a pseudo-clinical trial. Under normal circumstances, a true clinical trial involves recruiting individuals who are already sick

and the purpose of the clinical is to determine whether an intervention can prevent or alleviate symptoms of the sickness or death due to the sickness. However, in the case of vaccination against the disease caused by SARS-COV-2, one is determining whether vaccination with the Pfizer/BioNTech vaccine (BNT162b2mRNA) can prevent severe symptoms of COVID-19 as a result of SARS-COV-2 infections. The clinical trial of the Pfizer/BioNTech vaccine (BNT162b2mRNA) [6] has clearly failed as it could not determine whether BNT162b2mRNA can prevent death in vaccinated individuals because it did not recruit enough participants. Both DPV-10000 and DPUV-10000 were determined to be 0. All the clinical trial of the Pfizer/BioNTech vaccine (BNT162b2mRNA) [6] could state was that BNT162b2mRNA was 95 % effective at preventing severe symptoms of COVID-19, a highly dubious conclusion which was arrived at because 8 of the vaccinated participants develop COVID-19 whereas 162 unvaccinated participants develop COVID-19. The clinical trial of the Pfizer/BioNTech vaccine (BNT162b2mRNA) [6] does not state what prevailing pandemic condition the participants were subjected to: 1. Do the participants live in a crowded city or

suburban setting and what the population densities were, 2. what was the IP-10000 Number among the general population prior to the start of the clinical trial, and (3) What socio-economic strata do the participants belong to. Certain participants may be more careful than others. For example they may be more aware of the dangers of SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19, self-isolate, wear masks, wash their hands, eat well, take special nutrients, and be generally healthier, etc. The study of Dagan, N. et al. [27] shows clearly that in Israel, the effects of the Pfizer/BioNTech vaccine (BNT162b2mRNA) are very marginal (See above).

A proper clinical trial would consist of vaccinating the enrolled participants, challenging them with infectious SARS-COV-2 and then determining who develop severe symptoms of COVID-19. It is well established that BNT162b2mRNA does not prevent SARS-COV-2 infection (which is quite odd as it is directed against SARS-COV-2 encoded Spike protein which is necessary for binding to SARS-COV-2 receptor,). In view of the fact that there are healthy volunteers who are prepared to accept infectious SARS-COV-2 being injected into them [41,42], it is difficult to

understand why Pfizer/BioNTech does not want to determine whether its anti-SARS-CoV-2 vaccine, BNT162b2mRNA is truly effective or not.

The Moderna anti-SARS-CoV-2 vaccine (mRNA1273 SARS-CoV-2): The anti-SARS-CoV-2 vaccine developed by Moderna [43] is very similar to that developed by Pfizer/BioNTech in that its main ingredient is an mRNA molecule that encodes the SARS-CoV-2 Spike protein. According to the FDA [44], the Moderna anti-SARS-CoV-2 vaccine (mRNA1273 SARS-CoV-2) consists of the following: Each 0.5 mL dose of the Moderna COVID-19 Vaccine contains 100 mcg of a nucleoside-modified messenger RNA encoding the viral spike (S) glycoprotein of SARS-CoV-2. Each dose of the Moderna COVID-19 Vaccine also includes the following ingredients: lipids (SM-102; 1,2-dimyristoyl-rac-glycero-3-methoxypolyethylene glycol-2000 [PEG2000-DMG]; cholesterol; and 1,2-distearoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphocholine [DSPC]), tromethamine, tromethamine hydrochloride, acetic acid, sodium acetate, and sucrose. As with the anti-SARS-CoV-2 vaccine developed by Pfizer/BioNTech (BNT162b2mRNA) [6], it is quite surprising

that a vaccine that is be injected into billions of individuals is described as "100 mcg of a nucleoside-modified messenger RNA encoding the viral spike (S) glycoprotein of SARS-CoV-2. [44]. There is a big difference between 30 µg [6] and 100 µg [44] indicating that the mRNA molecule being used as an immunogen lacks specific molecular description. In general all the criticisms levied at the the anti-SARS-CoV-2 vaccine developed by Pfizer/BioNTech (BNT162b2mRNA) [6] are also valid for the Moderna anti-SARS-CoV-2 vaccine (mRNA1273 SARS-CoV-2) (See above).

According to the study of Baden, L.R. et al. [43], the Moderna anti-SARS-CoV-2 vaccine (mRNA1273 SARS-CoV-2) is 94.1 % effective base on the finding that 185 out of 15170 unvaccinated individuals develop symptoms of COVID-19 and 11 out of 15181 vaccinated individuals develop symptoms of COVID-19. Baden, L.R. [40] further states that 30 unvaccinated individuals developed severe symptoms of COVID-19 and 1 unvaccinated individual died whereas no vaccinated individuals developed severe symptoms of COV-19 or died. These results indicate that the effect if any of the Moderna anti-SARS-CoV-2 vaccine (mRNA1273 SARS-CoV-2) was a mirage. The IPV-

10000 Number and IPUV-10000 Number for the clinical trial of the Moderna anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine (mRNA1273 SARS-CoV-2) can be calculated to be ~ 7.2 and ~ 122 respectively (Figure 2A). There is an alarming discrepancy between the IPUV-10000 Number (~ 122) described by Baden, L.R. et al. [43] and the IPUV-10000 Number (~ 4) described by Polack et al. [6] (Compare Figure 1A and Figure 2A).

These results suggest that the Moderna anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine (mRNA1273 SARS-CoV-2) is not only ineffective but also extremely dangerous. The placebo in the clinical trial of the Moderna anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine (mRNA1273 SARS-CoV-2) is extremely dangerous because it caused an increase of IPUV-10000 from ~ 4 (the Pfizer/BioNTech vaccine, BNT162b2mRNA) [6] to ~ 122 (Moderna anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine, mRNA1273 SARS-CoV-2) [43]. Unless the discrepancy between the IPUV-10000 Number (~ 122) described by Baden, L.R. et al. [43] and the IPUV-10000 Number (~ 4) described by Pollock et al. [6] is resolved, it is legitimate to infer that Dishonest Scientific Reporting, Data Falsification and possibly Data Fabrication have occurred.

Figure 2. Panel A. Comparison of IPUV-10000 Number (Total Number of Individuals Infected with SARS-COV-2 and developing COVID-19 Per 10000 Unvaccinated Population) for the general population (I), IPUV-10000 Number Total Number of Individuals Infected with SARS-COV-2 and developing COVID-19 Per 10000 Unvaccinated Population) for the Moderna clinical trial (II) and IPV-10000 Number Total Number of Individuals Infected with SARS-COV-2 and developing COVID-19 Per 10000 Unvaccinated Population) for Moderna clinical trial (III). Panel B. Comparison of DPUV-10000 Number (Total Number of Deaths due to SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19 Per 10000 Unvaccinated Population) for the general population (I), IPUV-10000 Number (Total Number of Deaths due to SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19 Per 10000 Unvaccinated Population) for the Moderna clinical trial (II) and IPV-10000 Number (Total Number of Deaths due to SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19 Per 10000 Vaccinated Population) for Moderna clinical trial (III).

There are also major disturbing issues with the DPV-10000 Number and DPUV-10000 Number. The DPV-10000 Number can be calculated to be ~ 0.66 . The DPV-10000

could not be calculated because the clinical trial of the Moderna anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine (mRNA1273 SARS-CoV-2) did not enroll enough participants (Figure 2B). The DPUV-10000 Number of ~0.66 presented in the clinical trial of the Moderna anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine (mRNA1273 SARS-CoV-2) [43] is a lot lower than the DPP-10000 Number (Total Number of Deaths Per 10000 Population) of ~18 for the general population under prevailing pandemic condition [29] (Figure 2B).

Designing an experimental protocol in order to obtain a preconceived result and conclusion constitutes Data Falsification. Not highlighting and discussing that an experimental protocol has been designed so that a preconceived result and conclusion would be obtained constitutes Dishonest Scientific Report [28,29].

The Johnson & Johnson anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine (Ad26.COV2.S): The anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine developed by Johnson & Johnson (Ad26.COV2.S) [45] is distinct from the Pfizer/BioNTech vaccine (BNT162b2mRNA) [6] and Moderna vaccine (mRNA1273 SARS-CoV-2) [43] in that it is not a mRNA vaccine but the gene

encoding the SARS-COV-2 S protein is inserted into an Adenovirus which is then injected intra-muscularly. According to the FDA [46], the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine developed by Johnson & Johnson (Ad26.COV2.S) [45] consists of the following: The Janssen COVID-19 Vaccine does not contain a preservative. Each 0.5 mL dose of the Janssen COVID-19 Vaccine is formulated to contain 5×10^{10} virus particles of the Ad26 vector encoding the S glycoprotein of SARS-CoV-2. Each dose of the Janssen COVID-19 Vaccine also includes the following inactive ingredients 2.19 mg sodium chloride, 0.14 mg citric acid monohydrate, 2.02 mg trisodium citrate dihydrate, 0.16 mg. It is indeed quite disturbing that there is so little information about the exact molecular nature of the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine developed by Johnson & Johnson (Ad26.COV2.S) [45,46].

Sadoff et al. [45] states that the Johnson & Johnson vaccine (Ad26.COV2.S) is 66.9% effective on account of the fact that 116 participants out of 19630 vaccinated participants developed COVID-19 while 348 participants out of 19691 unvaccinated participants developed COVID-19. Sadoff et al. [45] also declared that the Johnson &

Johnson vaccine (Ad26.COV2.S) was 76.7 % and 85.4 % effective with respect to severe cases of COVID-19 14 days and 28 days after vaccination. The IPUV-10000 Number and IPV-10000 Number with respect to COVID-19 cases for the clinical trial of the Johnson & Johnson vaccine (Ad26.COV2.S) can be calculated to be ~176 and ~59 respectively. The DPUV-10000 Number and the DPV-10000 cannot be calculated most probably because not enough participants were recruited. The IPUV-10000 Number is reasonable compared to the IPUV-10000 Number of the general population (Figure 3A). However, the IPUV-10000 Number of ~176 is an alarming figure compared to the IPUV-10000 Number of ~4 for the clinical trial of the Pfizer/BioNTech vaccine (BNT162b2mRNA)[6] and IPUV-10000 Number of ~122 for the clinical trial of the Moderna vaccine (mRNA1273 SARS-CoV-2) [43] (Figure 4).

If the clinical trial of the Johnson & Johnson vaccine (Ad26.COV2.S) was designed and performed pursuant to the prevailing pandemic condition, logic dictates that the determined IPUV-10000 Number should be very similar to either of the IPUV-10000 numbers for the clinical trials of

Pfizer/BioNTech vaccine (BNT162b2mRNA) [6], Moderna vaccine (mRNA1273 SARS-CoV-2) [43].

Figure 3. Panel A, Comparison of IPUV-10000 Number (Total Number of Individuals Infected with SARS-COV-2 and developing COVID-19 Per 10000 Unvaccinated Population) for the general population (I), IPUV-10000 Number (Total Number of Individuals Infected with SARS-COV-2 and developing COVID-19 Per 10000 Unvaccinated Population) for the Johnson & Johnson clinical Trial (II), and IPV-10000 Number (Total Number of Individuals Infected with SARS-COV-2 and developing COVID-19 Per 10000 Vaccinated Population) (III) for the Johnson & Johnson clinical trial. Panel B, Comparison of DPUV-10000 Number (Total Number of Deaths Due to SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19 Per 10000 Unvaccinated Population) for the general population (I), DPUV-10000 Number (Total Number of Deaths Due to SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19 Per 10000 Unvaccinated Population) for the Johnson & Johnson clinical trial (II), and DPV-10000 Number (Total Number of Deaths Due to SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19 Per 10000 Vaccinated Population) for the Johnson & Johnson clinical trial.

The result of the clinical trial of Johnson & Johnson vaccine (Ad26.COV2.S) imply that the IPUV-10000 was over-inflated to camouflage the high IPV-10000 Number. The said result also suggest that the Placebo used in the clinical trial of Johnson & Johnson vaccine (Ad26.COV2.S) is highly dangerous (Figure 4). Thus, it is legitimate to make the supposition that Dishonest Scientific Report, Data Falsification and possibly Data Fabrication are associated with the clinical trial of the Johnson & Johnson vaccine (Ad26.COV2.S).

Conclusion: The effectiveness and safety of the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccines are exaggerated and unscientific (See Figures 1, 2, 3 and 4). The clinical trials of the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccines developed by Pfizer/BioNTech (BNT162b2mRNA), Moderna (mRNA1273 SARS-CoV-2) and Johnson & Johnson (Ad26.COV2.S) are tainted with Dishonest Scientific Reporting, Data Falsification and possibly Data Fabrication. In particular, the discrepancy in the IPUV-10000 Numbers (Total Number of Infected Individuals Per 100000 Unvaccinated Individuals) of ~4 for the Pfizer/BioNTech vaccine (BNT162b2mRNA), ~122 for the Moderna vaccine (mRNA1273 SARS-CoV-2), and ~

176 for the Johnson and Johnson vaccine (Ad26.COV2.S) is not only alarming but dangerous (Figure 4).

If the data of Baden, L.R. et al. [43] and Sadoff et al. [45] are to be taken at face value, it would suggest that the vaccine themselves and the placebos are dangerous. All the IPUV-10000 Numbers must be very similar and they are not (Figure 4). The IPUV-10000 Numbers from all three clinical trials must be very similar because they are not supposed to have any beneficial or adverse effects. They only serve as a reference point to determine and calculate the effects of interventions (i.e vaccination). It is interesting to note that in their study of the effectiveness of the

Pfizer/BioNTech vaccine (BNT162b2mRNA) and Moderna vaccine (mRNA1273 SARS-CoV-2), Pawlowski, C. et al. [48] concluded that "ICU admission rates were similar between these cohorts (1% vs. 1.3%; Relative Risk = 0.82; $p = 1.0$) (Figure 4B, Table 4). 14-day conditional mortality rates were also not significantly different (0% vs. 0.085%; Relative Risk = 0; $p = 1.0$)", In other words vaccinations did not improve the risks of being admitted to intensive care and dying. Pawlowski, C. et al [48] explained that "While the ICU admission and mortality rates were not significantly lower in our vaccinated population, this may be attributable to an inadequate number of patients with these outcomes in either group to date in our study. As more patients are vaccinated and follow-up time increases, we will update our analyses to determine whether vaccination can also reduce the risk of these outcomes". It is somewhat disingenuous to state that "FDA-authorized COV-19 vaccines are effective per real world evidence synthesized across multi-state health system" when the data shows clearly that the Pfizer/BioNTech vaccine (BNT162b2mRNA) and Moderna vaccine (mRNA1273 SARS-CoV-2), were not effective at preventing deaths of ICU admitted patients. (It is also worth noting that

the conclusions of Pawlowski, C. et al. [48] are being ignored and appears to be intentionally not advertised). It is interesting to note that from the data presented by Pawlowski, C. et al. [48], it can be calculated that the DPUV-10000 Number was 0.64 a figure which is lower than the DPUV-10000 Number of the general population (~18) but higher than DPUV-10000 Number of ~0.54 that could be calculated from the data presented by Dagan, N. et al. [27].

As the DPV-10000 Numbers for the clinical trials for the Pfizer/BioNTech vaccine (BNT162b2mRNA), Moderna vaccine (mRNA1273 SARS-CoV-2), and the Johnson and Johnson vaccine (Ad26.COV2.S) are very different, they suggest that the clinical trials have been badly designed or they have been designed to produce preconceived results and conclusions. It is clear that the clinical trials of the Pfizer/BioNTech vaccine (BNT162b2mRNA), Moderna vaccine (mRNA1273 SARS-CoV-2), and the Johnson and Johnson vaccine (Ad26.COV2.S) cannot be used to determine their efficacies and safety. Based on the study of Dagan, N. et al. [27], one can project that with mass vaccination and assuming maximum vaccination of the United States population, one would still register ~4,980

deaths (or DPV-10000 Number of ~0.15) compared to ~17928 deaths (or DPUV-10000 Number of ~0.54) every year if the United States population were not vaccinated (assuming that the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccine remains protective for one year) (Figure 5). If the United States were to practice strict Isolation/Confinement, Mask Wearing, Social Distancing, Testing, Contact Tracing and Treatment (IMSTCT), one would register significantly less deaths than with mass vaccination (Figure 5) as seen in a number of countries, including China, Singapore, Vietnam, Malaysia and Mauritius. Figure 5B also shows that even after full vaccination, the DPV-10000 Number (~1.5) will remain higher than the DPUV-10000 Numbers experienced in countries that practice only strict Isolation/Confinement, Mask Wearing, Social Distancing, Testing, Contact Tracing and Treatment (IMSTCT).

As the true effectiveness of the anti-SARS-COV-2 vaccines is questionable deaths due to SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19 will continue to be recorded unless there is complete or near eradication of SARS-COV-2. The biggest test will come in fall and winter of 2021-2022. It would seem that one would have to live with SARS-COV-2 as one

has learnt how to live with the Influenza virus.

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